

Reducing Linguistic Bias in Pedagogical Assessment through the *Triple A Method*

Dávid Szabó L.

PhD student, J. Selye University, Komárno, Slovakia

Abstract

Pedagogical assessment is a complex and multifaceted process that fundamentally shapes students' development and the functioning of the teaching-learning environment. The purpose of assessment is not only to measure knowledge but also to foster personality development, motivation, and adaptive regulation of the school environment. However, traditional pedagogical assessment methods often overlook students' linguistic and sociocultural backgrounds, which may lead to linguistic discrimination. This study aims to demonstrate how linguistic bias in pedagogical assessment, particularly in oral evaluations, can be reduced. For this purpose, we can apply the Triple A method (referred to as the BBB Method in Hungarian), developed by Lőrincz, Istók, and Baka L. (2022), which focuses on fostering linguistic tolerance and an accepting pedagogical attitude. The method incorporates three core principles which help avoid linguistic discrimination while promoting students' language development. The study highlights that pedagogical assessment not only serves to measure students' knowledge but also plays a significant role in encouraging the acceptance and respect of linguistic and cultural diversity, thereby contributing to the reduction of discrimination within the school environment.

Keywords: *pedagogical assessment, linguistic tolerance, linguistic discrimination, Triple A method.*

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Introduction

One of the everyday tasks of those entering or already engaged in the teaching profession is the assessment of students, which is not always easy, given the inherent complexity of educational assessment. This complexity is underscored by the fact that assessment is a fundamental component of personality development (Gardner 2013; Stiggins 2017), as well as a crucial element in effectively supporting learning (Deneen et al. 2019). When we speak of assessment, everyone has some idea of what it entails, yet the question remains whether we can clearly articulate what we actually mean by it. Even in early childhood, adults evaluated us, although we might not have referred to it as such at the time, when our actions were evaluated by a smile or a disapproving glance. According to Hercz (2007, 1) our environment responds to our actions, emotions, and outputs ergo it evaluates us. We perceive these reactions and, when

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necessary, adjust our behaviour, accordingly, striving to meet the expectations placed upon us. In this way, we develop and change throughout our lives from birth to old age. Thus, assessment is a constant presence in our everyday lives, a persistent factor in our development and life experiences, making it all the more important to consider who assesses us and how they do so.

Theoretical Overview

In the present study, we focus on pedagogical assessment as it is implemented in educational institutions. According to Golnhofer (2003, 335) pedagogical assessment refers to a comprehensive and methodologically diverse form of structured feedback and value judgment, encompassing education, instruction, and their respective levels, subsystems, objectives, participants, and content. Báthory (1985, 179) argues that when a teacher evaluates, they determine the degree of alignment between an expected and an actual state. Tóth and Horváth (2021) emphasize that through feedback, assessment influences the functioning of the entire educational process; it is this feedback mechanism that renders the system both regulated and adaptive. Assessment involves processes such as monitoring, judging, comparing, influencing, recognizing, and reinforcing (Szarka & Szabó L. 2024, 21). It is therefore no coincidence that pedagogical assessment plays a crucial role within the teaching-learning system (Molnár & Víg, 2013).

In a narrower sense, pedagogical assessment can be regarded as a method of both education and instruction (Hencz 2007). It functions as an educational method when it involves rewarding and recognizing, or conversely, punishing, and reproaching individuals (Bábosik 2003). It serves as an instructional method when its core purpose is to compare goals with achieved outcomes, to provide feedback, and to determine value across various levels and elements of education and instruction (Báthory 1997).

Pedagogical assessment fulfils twelve functions: feedback, reinforcement, monitoring, motivating, providing informing, guidance, regulating, correcting, diagnosis, prognosis, development, and selecting (Szarka & Szabó L. 2024, 24). These functions highlight the importance of teachers performing assessment as effectively as possible.

Depending on its form, assessment may be oral, written, or practical (Farkas 2019, 29). In this study, we focus specifically on oral assessment. This includes student responses given independently or guided by questions, reports, discussions, explanations, as well as student presentations and lectures.

Since one of the most important responsibilities of teachers in the school-based teaching and learning process is the assessment of students' knowledge and the measurement and evaluation of their development, the process of measurement and assessment must meet various methodological requirements. These include objectivity, reliability, and validity, which together are referred to as indicators of good measurement quality (Buda 2011, 5).

Objectivity means that the measured (assessed) result should depend solely on the properties and characteristics of what is being measured, so it must not be influenced by the individual conducting the measurement or assessment. In other words, the evaluation must be impartial. Ensuring objectivity is essential at every stage of the assessment process. Subjective factors must be excluded not only during the testing phase (data collection) but also during correction, evaluation (analysis), and interpretation of the results (Szarka & Szabó L. 2024, 29).

Reliability, also known as consistency or stability, refers to the degree to which a given measurement tool yields consistent results. In the context of testing, this means that the test must effectively measure what it is intended to measure. However, from the perspective of the present study, this aspect is not directly relevant.

Validity refers to whether we are truly measuring what we intend to measure. This presupposes a clear understanding of the construct or phenomenon we aim to assess. While it may seem self-evident that we are aware of our assessment goals, making the requirement for validity appear straightforward or even trivial, in practice, the situation is far more complex. When dealing with multifaceted phenomena, it is quite common to inadvertently measure something different from, or in addition to, what we originally intended. For example, when assessing scientific thinking through text-based problems, we may unintentionally measure students' reading comprehension skills as well. If the task's wording is overly lengthy or complex, we risk conflating poor comprehension with underperformance in scientific reasoning. In such cases, students' reading difficulties may be misinterpreted as deficiencies in their scientific thinking (Szarka & Szabó L. 2024, 30; Buda 2011).

According to Arató (2017, 21), one of the key insights regarding assessment is that it inherently contains a significant degree of subjectivity, even as it strives for objectivity. Therefore, the aim should not be to eliminate subjectivity altogether, but rather to recognize and consciously address it. In this process, a crucial role is played by the articulation and comparison of pre-existing pedagogical and assessment beliefs with scientifically grounded frameworks, particularly in the teacher training and teacher candidates.

The assessment of school knowledge can be conducted in various ways. At times, a teacher can immediately gauge a student's understanding, while in other cases, a student may need to respond at length before an evaluation can be made. Oral assessment is particularly time-consuming and can involve numerous subjective elements, which may influence the outcome of the evaluation (Szarka & Szabó L. 2024, 87). These subjective factors may include disagreements between teacher and student, the emotional state of either party at the time of assessment, or even the vernacular the student brings from home (Lőrincz, Istók & Baka L., 2022, p. 62).

According to Lippai (2021, 147), an oral exam is a performance that inevitably requires presentation skills. Consequently, extroverted, relaxed, and sociable personality traits are advantageous in oral examinations, whereas quieter, more introverted students must make a conscious effort to enhance their communication skills to achieve a good grade.

This is especially true when a child comes from an environment where a language variety different from the one expected at school is spoken. In a 1977 U.S. court case (Labov 1982, 167–174), the parents of African American children argued that Martin Luther King Elementary School in Ann Arbor failed to consider the students' sociocultural and linguistic backgrounds when assessing their mental and learning abilities.

As described by Lőrincz, Istók, and Baka L. (2022, 63), the school used aptitude tests that included language modules based on Standard English. However, the African American children spoke a home variety known as African American English (formerly referred to as Black English), which differs significantly from Standard English in both phonology and grammar. Based on expert linguistic testimony, the court ruled that the school's approach was discriminatory.

In his book *Nyelvi előítélet és diszkrimináció a magyartanári értékelésben* [Linguistic Prejudice and Discrimination in Hungarian Language Teaching Assessment], Jánk (2019, 13–16, 64–66, 194–199) presents the results of a large-scale study conducted among current and prospective Hungarian language teachers in the Carpathian Basin (including Hungary, Slovakia, Romania, and Ukraine). His research revealed that students' oral responses are often evaluated not so much based on the content of what they say, but rather on the variety of language they use and their manner of speaking (Bernstein 1975; Lőrincz & Istók 2023, 80).

Jánk's findings indicate that responses delivered in the standard language variety (Common Hungarian) and/or in an elaborated speech style (i.e., long, polished, well-structured sentences), even if lacking in substantive content, tend to receive higher grades from teachers than responses that contain all essential information but are delivered in a regional dialect and/or a restricted speech style (characterized by short, repetitive sentences). In other words, Hungarian language teachers are more likely to evaluate the manner of speaking rather than the actual knowledge being demonstrated, often guided by implicit biases.

It is important to note, however, that teachers are frequently unaware of these biases (Lőrincz & Istók 2023, 80).

However, the results of Jánk's research contradict the already described quality criteria, which are the various measurement methodological requirements of the measurement-evaluation process (Table 1).

Contradictions to Quality Criteria in Jánk's (2019) Findings

Quality indicator	Characteristics of the quality indicator	Counterexample in Jánk's (2019) study
<i>Objectivity</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ The measured (evaluated) result must depend solely and exclusively on the properties and characteristics of the object being measured. ◆ The outcome of the measurement–evaluation must not be influenced by the person conducting the measurement or evaluation. ◆ The evaluation must not be biased. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Teachers tend to give higher grades to responses expressed in a standard language variety and/or an elaborated speech style, even if the content is weaker, than to responses that contain all essential information but are delivered in a dialect and/or a restricted speech style.
<i>Reliability</i>	This study does not examine this.	
<i>Validity</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Whether we are truly measuring what we intend to measure ◆ In complex phenomena, it is very easy to measure something entirely different or additional to our original intention 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ The Hungarian language teacher evaluates not the knowledge itself, but primarily the manner of speaking (based on their biases).

Source: own table based on Jánk's Findings (2019)

This phenomenon, however, can occur during oral assessments in any subject. The teacher's evaluation is influenced by the risk of linguistic discrimination, which may lead the student to feel that studying is pointless, as the teacher does not appreciate their efforts (Lőrincz, Istók & Baka L. 2022, 64).

Jánk (2019, 198) notes that this is nothing other than the “Pygmalion effect, or self-fulfilling prophecy: the child eventually identifies with the role that corresponds to the teacher’s (and society’s) prior expectations and assumptions. [...] The ultimate consequence is that many talented students are lost at a very early stage, which is not only a huge problem and mistake for the affected children but also for society as a whole.”

The Triple A Method

To overcome linguistic discrimination, Lőrincz and Istók (2023, 81) developed *The Triple A Method*¹, which can serve as a useful tool for the conscious development of linguistic tolerance. In the short term, this method may help eliminate teachers’ negative remarks about students’ language use and in the long term, it may contribute to extending the resulting shift in perspective to pedagogical assessment.

Why is this necessary? Because a 2022 study (Lőrincz, Istók & Baka L. 2022, 66–69) found that half of its respondents reported that Hungarian language teachers regularly corrected students in primary and secondary education who used nonstandard elements or forms (e.g., regional words, slang, foreign words) during lessons.

According to Istók, Lőrincz, and Török (2025, 44), the classroom is the part of the school least exposed to top-down influences; therefore, the absence of visual representation of nonstandard elements (e.g., dialectal or slang) can be interpreted as a particular form of self-discrimination, since the posters and images displayed in classrooms exclusively represent the Hungarian standard (Bartha, Laihonon & Szabó 2013, 21).

To this end, one of the most important tasks during pedagogical assessment is to improve the negative evaluation of nonstandard elements, that is, to educate for linguistic tolerance. We hold the same view regarding students’ expressive skills and presentation style. If correction or feedback is necessary (and it should be) from the teacher, it should not diminish the value of the oral response. Furthermore, corrections should be carried out using the Triple Method, thereby helping to prevent linguistic prejudice, stigmatization, and discrimination from occurring in (Hungarian) schools.

The Triple A Method (Lőrincz, Istók & Baka L. 2022, 71–74) was developed to foster a linguistically tolerant pedagogical attitude, integrating well-known sociolinguistic approaches into a single acronym consisting of uniform elements (Figure 1).

The function of this *mnemonics*² is to remind us that it is only worth making comments on non-standard elements or forms used by students in ADDITIVE LANGUAGE APPROACH, with an AMICABLE ATTITUDE and in connection with the ADEQUATE SPEECH SITUATION, instead of replacing the justification with the standard form.

The first A like *Additive language approach*. Our language cultivation often engages in language-impoverishing activities rather than language enrichment, even today, by opposing foreign words, slang, dialect words, or forms considered ungrammatical. However, teachers should strive to expand existing knowledge elements with new

¹ The authors refer to this as the SSS Method (Istók, Lőrincz & Török 2025, 39), but in our opinion, the AAA better captures the essence of the model.

² Mnemonics are learning aids that are used to store and recall information that is more difficult to remember (Antalné 2008; Istók, Tóth & N. Varagya 2021; Istók, Lőrincz & Török 2023).

ones, enabling students to feel comfortable and at ease in various speech situations. The goal is for teachers to familiarize students with the standard equivalents of foreign words, slang, or dialect words. When students use words different from the standard language, teachers should not respond by labelling those words as “bad” or discouraging their use; instead, they should offer alternatives with the intention of enrichment. Multiple reinforcement, alongside memorization, serves precisely to give students a sense of success in different verbal communication contexts. This accepting, child-developmentally beneficial attitude is called an additive language perspective (Lőrincz & Istók 2023, 82–83).

Figure 1. The Triple A Method

Source: own figure based on Lőrincz, Istók & Baka 2022, 71

The second A like *Amicable attitude*. Labelling dialect words, slang, or foreign words brought from home or peer environments with negative terms implies the exclusivity of standard forms and, at the same time, the inferiority of the vernacular (local) language varieties. Teachers’ prescriptive (norm-enforcing) and subtractive (replacement-oriented) language attitudes can negatively affect children’s emotional development. If children constantly hear that they speak Hungarian incorrectly, badly, or poorly, they begin to question their native language variety brought from home (the language spoken by their parents, grandparents, relatives, etc.) causing damage to their identity and self-confidence. The ongoing stigmatization and labelling of their native language variety may result in the child becoming withdrawn and less communicative in class. We are convinced that introducing the standard language variety with a friendly attitude (while respecting children’s dialects) is also achievable (Lőrincz & Istók 2023, 83–84).

The third A like *Adequate speech situation*. Every natural human language exists in language varieties (so-called lects), and each variety has its own system of norms (rules). Although competence development in kindergartens and schools largely focuses on learning the elements and forms of the standard language variety, the appropriateness (suitability) of linguistic and stylistic expressive means depends not on the standard

language variety but on the speech situation. However, we cannot expect children to use the standard variety in every speech situation (Lőrincz & Istók 2023, 84–85).

Lanstyák (1998, 17) compares the question of linguistic appropriateness to clothing: *“Just as it would be inappropriate to go to the theatre in a tracksuit, it would be equally improper to wear a suit to play football or dig a pit latrine. Language is no different: there are occasions where so-called careful speech is appropriate; in other situations, so-called casual speech is the most suitable, and there are times when so-called laid-back speech is natural.”*

Therefore, it is important to inform students about which words are appropriate in which linguistic situations.

Conclusion

Overall, it can be said that there is a close theoretical and practical connection between pedagogical assessment and the *Triple A Method*, especially concerning oral evaluation and the issue of linguistic discrimination. This connection can be grasped through three main directions:

1. Alignment with the goals and functions of pedagogical assessment: The aim of pedagogical assessment is not only to measure knowledge, but also to support student development, motivation, reinforcement, and the provision of positive feedback. The Triple A Method directly contributes to these functions by encouraging teacher responses to student language use that are friendly, non-rejective, and oriented toward enrichment.

If a student uses a dialect word during an oral exam, the teacher should not automatically downgrade their performance based on that alone. Instead, according to the Triple A Method, the teacher can offer the standard equivalent, thereby simultaneously acknowledging and developing the student.

2. Protecting measurement methodological principles (especially validity): One of the fundamental criteria of good assessment is validity: are we truly measuring what we intend to measure? In the case of oral evaluation, validity is jeopardized when teachers (perhaps unconsciously) assess language use (e.g., vocabulary, dialect, sentence length) rather than content knowledge.

The Triple A Method helps preserve validity by making teachers aware of their own linguistic biases; by emphasizing that language use and knowledge are distinct categories that must be assessed separately; and by preventing nonstandard language use from leading to discrimination.

According to Jánk’s research, teachers tend to give higher grades to answers that are eloquently phrased but weaker in content. The Triple A Method is designed to dismantle this form of linguistic distortion in assessment.

3. Conscious management of subjective distorting factors in oral assessment: Pedagogical assessment (especially oral evaluation) can involve many subjective elements (e.g., mood, linguistic bias). According to Arató (2017), the goal is not to eliminate subjectivity but to become aware of and manage it. The Triple A Method supports exactly this: additive language approach reduces binary thinking in terms of "correct vs. incorrect" language use; amicable attitude supports the student’s self-confidence and linguistic identity; adequate speech situation promotes the accurate, context-sensitive evaluation of language competence.

Thus, the Triple A Method fosters not only linguistic tolerance but also more conscious and equitable pedagogical assessment.

The quality of pedagogical assessment significantly influences students' development, self-image, and academic success. The *Triple A Method* is not merely a linguistic approach, but a tool to ensure that assessment aligns with modern, equitable pedagogical principles. Together, they represent an educational culture that values not only knowledge, but also the students' individual personalities.

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